

A Framework for Industry 4.0-Related Organizational Transformation

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Abstract. The global landscape is undergoing a profound shift from the industrial age to the cyber-physical era, where interconnected products and services wield significant influence over both society at large and individual organizations. As a distinctive form of strategic change, digital transformation reshapes the way value is created within organizations, emphasizing the need for continuous renewal of organizational capabilities to drive this evolution successfully. In an attempt to guide an organizational transformation roadmap, this study adopted a design science research (DSR) approach to develop a comprehensive framework to assist organizations in navigating Industry 4.0 transformation. The iterative DSR cycles of awareness, suggestion, development, evaluation, and conclusion were systematically applied, utilizing diverse data collection methods. The resultant framework encompasses 15 key organizational capabilities, 4 supporting capabilities and 9 monitoring mechanisms, intricately linked to the dynamic capabilities of sensing, seizing, transforming, and supporting. Moreover, these capabilities are strategically prioritized to guide organizations through the complexities of transformation, with embedded monitoring mechanisms facilitating real-time assessment. The operationalization of the framework through visualization and application guidelines furnishes organizations with a lucid roadmap for comprehending and prioritizing their Industry 4.0 transformation journey.

Keywords: Industry 4.0, digital transformation, organizational capabilities, organizational digital transformation.

1 Introduction

Digital transformation is a strategic response to digital technology trends and became a strategic imperative rather than just a technology implementation [1]. Facing the challenge of digital transformation and addressing the need to remain competitive, organizations must articulate and execute strategies that consider digital transformation implications and enhanced operational performance [2]. According to Li [3], digital transformation is described as the modern struggle to survive the threat of digital disruption so as to successfully manage the transition between the current and future organization. Furthermore, the recalibration of the organization's transformation path must be informed by frequently evaluating progress [4, 5].

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Notwithstanding the substantial expected impact of Industry 4.0 and digital transformation, organizations struggle with overseeing the complexity of the organization [6-8]. Hence, organizations must be empowered to drive digital transformation and create business value by attending to priorities that will add the most value to the organization [9, 10]. Because of digital transformation strategies, strategic management processes and organizational capabilities considered within the prospects and challenges brought about by Industry 4.0 [11], the purpose of this study is to establish the components and application of a framework that will guide organizations in Industry 4.0 transformation.

Therefore, this paper investigates the following research question: “*What are the components of a framework that will guide organizations regarding Industry 4.0 transformation?*”. By understanding the components of a framework that will guide organizations regarding Industry 4.0 transformation, organizations will be able to better understand and execute Industry 4.0 related transformation,

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 contains an overview of the literature and the research approach in Section 3. In section 4 we present a discussion on the findings, while section 5 details the contribution of the study. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 Background

The world is changing significantly as the era of the cyber-physical world, where connected products and services have broad consequences for society in general and organizations specifically, replaces the industrial era [12-14]. Worldwide, the rapid development of digital technology fundamentally shifted organizational strategies and operations [3].

2.1 Strategic organizational perspectives of industry 4.0

The technological and conceptual understanding of Industry 4.0 has evolved significantly since its initial German conception in 2011 [15]. The evolution of digital technologies, interconnectedness, smart systems, and cyber-physical systems, as well as the application of these technologies in digital transformation strategies in organizations, enriched the concept and understanding of Industry 4.0 [12-14]. Digital transformation in organizations is characterized by increased automation and data-driven decision making, resulting in a digital convergence between organizational business models, internal operations, and business processes [16-18]. Furthermore, organizations are better positioned to meet customer demands based on intelligent cyber-physical systems that are enabled to make autonomous decisions [15, 19]. Hence, Nosalska, Piątek [16:849] define Industry 4.0 as “a concept of organizational and technological changes along with value chains integration and new business models development that are driven by customer needs and mass customization requirements and enabled by innovative technologies, connectivity and information technology integration”.

The successful deployment of these organizational and technological changes hinges on factors that vary from executive management involvement, team capabilities and clearly defined strategies, rather than just on the technology itself [6]. Organizations,

therefore, must be able to drive digital value chains, thus creating more agile and market-focused competencies [9, 10].

2.2 Organizational and technological transformation strategies

To cope with the organizational and technological transformation related to Industry 4.0, organizations need to fully appreciate the complex characteristics of Industry 4.0 [20, 21]. Therefore, digital transformation strategies have to be conceptualized in terms of technological changes, as well as in terms of organizational dimensions, such as strategy, business process, people, internal support functions and culture [6] to realize sustainable competitive advantage [9, 22]. Hence, digital transformation strategies are driven by organizational value creation, with an emphasis on automation and digitalization [9, 23].

From a business perspective, the benefits of enabling technologies relate to operational benefits (e.g. production development and production quality), managerial benefits (e.g. continuous improvement and risk management), strategic benefits (e.g. product innovation and sustainability) and organizational benefits (e.g. improved working conditions and worker assistance) [17, 24, 25]. Considering digital transformation strategies in the context of opportunities and challenges presented by Industry 4.0, organizations have to rethink their business models, operating models, products, services and processes [11]. As digital transformation represents a specific type of strategic change, where business value is created through digital assets, organizations need to consider their retort to digital technology trends as a strategic response [11, 26].

2.3 Industry 4.0 capabilities, digital transformation capabilities and dynamic capabilities

Based on the definition of Industry 4.0 (refer to section 2.2) and the Industry 4.0-related organizational capabilities required, its particular interrelationship to organizational digital transformation must be contextualized [27]. Industry 4.0 drives transformation in organizations, and the practical implementation impacts both the digital and non-digital aspects of the organization [28]. Hence, as Industry 4.0 holds the potential to improve technology- and capabilities-based innovation, the utility of its applications is captured in a digital transformation strategy [27]. Bhattacharya and Momaya [27] capture the drivers of such an Industry 4.0-inclusive digital transformation strategy by identifying global industry trends, new technologies and innovation, and competitiveness as leading drivers. Bhattacharya and Momaya [27] identified existing delivery processes and networks, organization culture and existing standard operating procedures as drivers that may offer resistance to change. Peerally, Santiago [29] identified Industry 4.0 technological capabilities to be incorporated into organizational transformation: retrofitting and readiness capabilities (legacy operation integration and technology acquisition), system integration capabilities (physical-digital technology integration and prototyping), enhanced horizontal and vertical digitalization capabilities (critical digitalization needs identification and implementation across the organization) and smart-intelligent capabilities (self-optimization and scaling).

Incorporating Industry 4.0 capabilities is transversal as it cuts across the entire organization in a dynamic and non-linear digital transformation process [29]. Understanding the context of Industry 4.0 and digital transformation capabilities enables organizations to address specific strategy dilemmas during digital transformation implementation [27, 28].

Dynamic capabilities, as defined by Teece [30], involve a organization's ability to sense changes in its environment, seize new opportunities, and transform its resources and processes accordingly. Sensing refers to the capacity to detect market shifts and technological advancements, seizing involves the rapid deployment of resources to capitalize on identified opportunities and finally, transforming involves the adaptation and reconfiguration of internal capabilities to sustain competitive advantage over time.

2.4 Industry 4.0 and digital transformation capabilities' monitoring mechanisms

As organizational capabilities aid competitive advantage, differentiation, flexibility, innovation, a knowledgeable workforce and responsiveness to changes in the dynamic business environment, they have a direct impact on an organization's viability [31, 32]. Scholars widely recognize the practice in organizations to measure organizational performance based on strategy implementation and execution objectives [5, 33, 34]. However, a lack of appropriate resources and capabilities may hinder efficacy in an organization [5]. To remain competitive, deal with transformative change and navigate digital complexity, organizations must constantly renew their organizational capabilities [35, 36]. Adaku, Ankrah and Ndekugri [36:6] studied capability measurement constructs and identified "resources, ability, integration, governance and management system, task, and superior performance, as components". Adaku, Ankrah and Ndekugri [36] posit that these tangible and intangible components must be integrated within a management and governance system to ensure superior organizational performance. Therefore, organizational capability measurement instruments are tools that aim to assess the level and quality of an organization's ability to perform certain tasks or functions [37-39].

3 Methodology

This study aimed to design a framework that will guide organizations regarding Industry 4.0 transformation and applied a DSR to design the utility [40]. DSR applies a process whereby a new artefact is created [40]. When the knowledge required for designing the artefact does not exist, a research process must be followed to gain the required knowledge and build the artefact. This artefact can then be evaluated, and feedback can be provided to improve the artefact, resulting in an iterative and incremental process [40].

The study concluded 4 design steps, each with its unique data collection and data analysis methods to create the framework for Industry 4.0 transformation summarized in Table 1. For each design step, the data collection and data analysis methods are specified.

Table 1. Design Science Research steps to develop framework.

Design Step	Design step purpose	Data collection method	Data Analysis method
1	Defined Industry 4.0 strategic organizational perspective	Systematic Literature Review	Thematic analysis and axial coding
2	Identified key organizational capabilities impacted by Industry 4.0	Semi-structured interviews	Thematic analysis
3	Identified key organizational capabilities related to Industry 4.0 Prioritized key Industry 4.0 organizational capabilities towards organizational transformation	Semi-structured interviews	Thematic analysis and thematic network graphs Thematic analysis
4		Expert interviews	

The data collection, data analysis and framework design are discussed in the next section for each design cycle. For each step, the detailed data tables are available on a link to the data as the following sections only contains the summary of findings.

4 Findings and discussion

4.1 Step 1: Defined Industry 4.0 strategic organizational perspective

Data was collected by conducting a systematic literature review. A rigorous, stand-alone and systematic methodological approach must be used for an structured literature review to deliver optimal results [41]. The process defined by Boland, Cherry and Dickson [42] was chosen for this study and consisted of three steps: planning the review, conducting the review and reporting the review. The keywords chosen were “4IR” and “strategic alignment” and “organisation”; “fourth industrial revolution” and “strategic alignment” and “organisation”; and “I4.0” and “strategic alignment” and organisation”. After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, as well as quality assurance, 37 papers were analyzed in detail identifying 10 Industry 4.0 related organizational capability themes through descriptive codes [38] and through open coding to identify emerging main themes [39]. The 10 themes identified related to a strategic organizational perspective of Industry 4.0 included external drivers, Industry 4.0 relevant strategy, business value, workforce, technology, customer value, process, data, organizational change, and product. The first version of the framework that will guide organizations regarding Industry 4.0 transformation is shown in Table 2. The detailed data may be access here: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379189640_41_-Step_1_Defined_Industry_40_strategic_organizational_perspective.

Table 2. Framework version 1 for Industry 4.0-related organizational transformation.

Strategic alignment domain	Industry 4.0-related aspect
Service level	Human-centric organisational change
	Workforce education, productivity and wellbeing
	Customer experience differentiation

Competitive potential	Process optimisation and value chain digitalisation
	Product customisation and portfolio innovation
Technology potential	Data and Big Data management towards data-driven decision making
	Technology-centric convergence and digital ecosystem potential
Strategy execution	Market and industry external drivers and disruption
	Industry 4.0-relevant strategy and organisational structural alignment
	Business value improvement through digital business model innovation

4.2 Step 2: Identified key organizational capabilities impacted by Industry 4.0

Data for this step was collected via semi-structured interviews. Based on the outcome of Step 1 (Section 4.1), a semi-structured interview guide was designed. This guide consisted of two sections. Firstly, respondent demographic information (e.g. organizational level and tenure). Secondly, questions regarding key Industry 4.0 organizational capabilities. Purposive sampling was used to select the nine respondents, guided by the respondent's experience and knowledge relating to the research study [43]. The semi-structured interview data was analyzed using content analysis. According to Krippendorff [44], content analysis is a technique for analyzing audio, visual or textual content to identify underlying themes, patterns and meanings. It systematically organizes and interprets this content to draw inferences and insights regarding specific research objectives. In addition, for version 2 of the framework, the organizational capabilities were mapped to the dynamic capabilities defined by Teece [45] shown in Table 3. Color coding was applied to improve readability and associations related to the organizational dynamic capability columns. The 10 Industry 4.0 related organizational capability themes identified in step 1 were confirmed by the interviewees and were enriched with 4 additional themes identified in the semi-structured interviews. The detailed data may be access here: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379189728_41_-Step_2_Identified_key_organizational_capabilities_impacted_by_Industry_40.

Table 3. Framework version 2 for Industry 4.0-related organizational transformation.

Strategic alignment domain	Organisational dynamic capabilities			
	Sensing	Seizing	Transforming	Supporting
Service level			Customer experience differentiation	Human-centric organisational change
			Organisational culture and continuous learning	Workforce education, productivity and wellbeing
Competitive potential		Product customisation and portfolio innovation	Process optimisation and value chain digitalisation	Talent management, continuous learning and expertise domain development
			Efficient product delivery and product personalisation	
Technology potential	Data and Big Data management towards data-driven decision making	Technology-centric convergence and digital ecosystem potential		
		Competitive solutions development and services provider relationship management		

Strategy execution	Market and industry external drivers and disruption	Business value improvement through digital business model innovation	Industry 4.0-relevant strategy and organisational structural alignment	Communications and information sharing tools and personalisation
	Strategic leadership accountability, initiatives and objectives	Informed and data-driven decision making	Virtual and differentiated new and/or optimised business models	

4.3 Step 3: Identified key organizational capabilities related to Industry 4.0

The objective of this step was to understand the key organizational capabilities related to Industry 4.0 and how organizations can monitor these capabilities. Data for this step was collected using a semi-structured interview process. A semi-structured interview guide was designed based on the findings from steps 1 and 2 i.e., the questions were informed based on the strategic alignment domains and the Industry 4.0-relevant organizational capabilities. Eighteen purposive sampled respondents of all industry types and organizational levels were identified to get a broader perspective across organizations. The interviews were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis, specifically thematic networks. Thematic networks are web-like schematic diagrams that show the relationship between basic, organized and global themes [43, 46]. The process of creating thematic networks from the interview data starts with identifying basic themes in the data. Basic themes are identified by assigning initial labels and then grouping them according to organizing themes based on relatable data. Lastly, organizing themes are grouped together into global themes. In this step, the 14 Industry 4.0 related dynamic organizational capabilities were enriched to 18 Industry 4.0 key organizational capabilities and nine capability monitoring mechanisms shown in Table 4. The detailed data may be accessed here: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379216067_Section_43_Step_3_Identified_key_organizational_capabilities_related_to_Industry_40_Industry_Sector_of_Participants_Number_Participant_level_in_the_organisation.

Table 4. Framework version 3 for Industry 4.0-related organizational transformation.

Organisational dynamic capabilities			
Sensing	Seizing	Transforming	Supporting
Data and Big Data management towards data-driven decision making	Product customisation and portfolio innovation	Customer experience differentiation	Human-centric organisational change
Market and industry external drivers and disruption	Technology-centric convergence and digital ecosystem potential	Organisational culture and continuous learning	Workforce education, productivity and wellbeing
Strategic leadership accountability, initiatives and objectives	Competitive solutions development and services provider relationship management	Process optimisation and value chain digitalisation	Talent management, continuous learning and expertise domain development
	Business value improvement through digital business model innovation	Efficient product delivery and product personalisation	Communications and information-sharing tools and personalisation
	Informed and data-driven decision-making	Industry 4.0-relevant strategy and organisational structural alignment	
		Virtual and differentiated new and/or optimised business models	
Monitoring mechanisms			

Monitor competitive advantage and new developments	Monitor efficacy in product delivery, improve product versatility and digitally driven production	Continually monitoring the organisation's business value through repeat business	Monitor technology architectures, interconnectedness and business solutions for customers and workforce
Monitor global drivers, regulation and compliance		Monitor customer experience optimisation and improve the customer touchpoint processes	Monitor and improve workforce digital literacy
Monitor analysis and derivation of data-driven insight towards organisational innovation and new ways of working		Monitor optimised processes through process governance and automation	

4.4 Step 4: Prioritized key Industry 4.0 organizational capabilities towards organizational transformation

In the final DSR step, version 3 of the framework for Industry 4.0-related organizational transformation was evaluated by four industry experts by means of a semi-structured interview. The semi-structured interview guide was designed to understand the framework's utility from an organizational perspective and the summarized feedback from the respondents that impacted the final visualization of the framework.

The initial response to the framework from all interviewees was positive. All interviewees confirmed that the framework comprehensively covered industry 4.0-related organizational capabilities. In addition, the proposed capability prioritization of the frameworks received very positive comments, and interviewees confirmed that the framework would support the creation of an organizational roadmap for digital transformation. The interviewees also confirmed that the framework was visually appealing, and easy to understand and to follow. Positive feedback was also shared on the monitoring mechanisms as interviewees reflected that the framework generally provided concepts only, without the addition of monitoring these concepts. Two interviewees noted the importance of realizing that not all organizations are mature enough to handle every capability. Therefore, the organizations capabilities must first be determined before being guided on a digital transformation journey. Interviewee 4 remarked that the organizational transformation process is not always so formal or straightforward. Sometimes, an external event can force transformation onto an organization without proper time or investment into sensing and seizing. Additionally, interviewees agreed that Industry 4.0 is mainly connected to differentiation and the ability of an organization to set itself apart from other similar organizations.

Interviewees 2 and 4 agreed that data is key in Industry 4.0 organizational transformation, supporting that the sensing capability data and Big Data management towards data-driven decision-making must be a high priority. Additionally, interviewee 2 emphasized that organizations can only be transformed through their organizational capabilities. All interviewees noted that prioritizing and monitoring the organizational capabilities part of the framework will cause them to choose this framework more readily over other similar frameworks.

After applying the feedback from the expert interview, the resultant framework encompassed 15 key organizational capabilities, 4 supporting capabilities and 9

monitoring mechanisms (refer section 5 and visualization in Fig.1. The detailed data may be access here: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379218013_Section_44_-Step_4_Prioritized_key_Industry_40_organizational_capabilities_towards_organizational_transformation.

5 Framework for Industry 4.0 organizational transformation

The framework depicted in Figure 1 that will guide organizational transformation regarding Industry 4.0 was developed through 4 design science research steps. This framework consists of 18 organizational capabilities distributed over four dynamic capabilities: sensing, seizing, transforming, and supporting. The supporting dynamic capability operates across sensing, seizing, and transforming. Additionally, the 18 organizational capabilities are prioritized, and monitoring mechanisms are provided to aid organizations to monitor each capability as the organization transforms.

When organizations start a transformation journey, they must consider the importance of managing organizational outcomes and consequences related to Industry 4.0, specifically considering both the organizational and technological dimensions. Organizational capabilities, such as strategy, business processes, workforce skills, culture, and business models, play a crucial role in this transformation. However, organizations face financial constraints, resistance to change, lack of planning and skills, standardization and technology integration issues, and the absence of feasibility studies and business cases. Therefore, for efficient and effective organizational transformation, organizational capabilities can be prioritized to address challenges and ensure optimal resource allocation aligned with business value creation.

To guide organizations to effective and efficient industry 4.0-related transformation, the organizational capabilities were included as priorities. Hence, under the sensing dynamic capability, all three organizational capabilities, data and Big Data, external drivers, and strategic leadership, were highly prioritized. For the seizing dynamic capability, the product organizational capability was assigned high priority and business value was assigned a medium to high priority. The organizational capabilities of software services and solutions, and decision making were assigned a medium priority. Finally, the technology organizational capability was assigned a low priority.

For the transforming dynamic capability, the product efficacy organizational capability was assigned a high priority, and the process was assigned a medium to high priority. The organizational capability Industry 4.0-relevant strategy was assigned a medium priority. Finally, the organizational capabilities customer value, organization and business model were assigned a low priority. The high-priority organizational capability for supporting dynamic capability is skills and expertise. The workforce organizational capability was assigned a medium priority, and the organizational capabilities organizational change and communication were assigned a low priority.

Fig. 1. Framework for Industry 4.0 -related organizational transformation.

6 Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to establish the components and application of a framework that will guide organizations in Industry 4.0 transformation. The framework for Industry 4.0 -related organizational transformation was designed through four steps of design

science research and the resultant framework encompasses 15 key organizational capabilities, 4 supporting capabilities and 9 monitoring mechanisms, intricately linked to the dynamic capabilities of sensing, seizing, transforming, and supporting. Due to the impact of digital transformation strategies and the challenges and opportunities presented by Industry 4.0, the developed framework will assist organizations in navigating their transformation journey within this context.

The study specifically targeted organizations from various industries for interviews and questionnaires; however, it is important to acknowledge that the participants did not encompass representatives from all industry sectors. Consequently, the study may not fully capture the spectrum of organizations possessing capabilities for digital transformation. Additionally, it is noteworthy that the research focused exclusively on organizations in South Africa, limiting the geographical scope of the study to a specific region. This geographical constraint implies that the findings may be influenced by the unique contextual factors and business environments prevalent in South Africa, potentially impacting the generalizability of the results to a global context. Therefore, the study's outcomes should be interpreted within the context of its industry and geographical limitations.

Regarding recommended future research, an option is to apply the framework in real-world scenarios as a use case study. This use case could add valuable insight into the framework's utility in an organizational context and further enrich the framework.

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